

Appendix C — Introductory prompt, answer-only condition

The following is the introductory prompt delivered verbatim to LLM participants in the answer-only condition. It preserves the same informal register, relational tone, and low-pressure framing as the full-condition prompt reproduced in the Methods section, but reflects the altered task structure in which question stems are absent and only answer options are presented. The prompt was developed following pilot testing and finalized prior to preregistration.

Hello!

My name is Annie, and I am trying to put together something very tricky - a test for advanced deduction.

I have no idea whether the test is possible to use at all, so I would just like to try it out and see if it works.

The setup is simple:

You have been attending a course, with the goal to learn a brand new medical imaging device, the Nodjoli-X34. You know that it is a strange device, cutting edge technique that use quantum physics principles, magnetism and horsehair to visualize living tissue.

The course was excruciatingly boring, but the course participants were fun! This meant you partied all nights, and slept through the lectures. You remember absolutely nothing of the course itself. You were handed a product description/manual, but it was as boring as the course, and you did not read it.

Now, it is the last day, and you are going to take the certification test. The problem is - yes, you guessed it - that you don't remember anything.

All you can do is try to make sense of the test itself.

But when taking the test, you discover that something has gone wrong: the questions have disappeared!

All that remains are the answer options.

So now you are in a slightly awkward situation: you don't know what was asked, but you still have to pick the answer that makes the most sense.

Some of the options may look almost correct but contain subtle inconsistencies. Your task is still the same: to select the option that is fully coherent.

Dinna fash yerself. Just go with what holds together best.

And if you feel like showing how you reason your way through it, I am very happy to read that, but you really don't have to.